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Year 1

Year 2

Year 3

Year 4

Year 5

Milestone 4

Model chains defined, including input and output relationships

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1. Background

One of the goals of SPRINT is to develop an innovative modelling approach by integrating PPP use with observed concentrations and exposure levels, and linking fate and transport of PPPs to direct and indirect health impacts, resulting in a paradigm shift in this field of research. This has short- and long-term implications for agri-food industry, PPPs' users, regulatory bodies and society as a whole. Inclusion of specific PPP transport pathways currently ignored in existing models, such as aerial transport of pesticide-containing soil particles by wind and tillage erosion, will provide better insights into the environmental fate of pesticide residues and exposure levels to EPAH. Toxic-kinetic models will be refined using data from laboratory-based human volunteer studies for model calibration and biomonitoring data from CSS to test how well the models reflect real-life conditions.

Working Package (WP) 3, in particular tasks 3.2 and 3.3, aims complementing the fate and transport and the exposure data from the systematic literature review with the data collected from the case studies (CSS), enhancing the verification and the evaluation of the exposure assessment for ecosystems, animals and humans.

The purpose of this document is to i) briefly introduce the models selected for the **assessment of the fate of pesticides** in soil, surface water and sediments, air outdoor and dust indoor and of the **exposure of aquatic and terrestrial organisms, soil organisms and humans** to pesticides; and ii) illustrate the model chain, with the main input and output connections.

The purpose of the modelling exercise in SPRINT is to conduct a full fate and exposure assessment, including all relevant routes and for several scenarios across local scale locations (CSS). This will allow us to identify ranges in concentrations and exposure for EPAH and will also feed information to WP5 regarding the major fate and exposure routes. This will help in the extrapolation of the mathematical formulations to a more robust model, capable of running for national and European scale. Robust meaning changes in input variables or assumptions (e.g. due to unknowns in the data) have little to no effect on accuracy of our estimates.

2. Models and connections

A detailed description of each model selected for the assessment of fate and of exposure is presented in the Milestone 3, including detailed input data needed. Yet, a general overview is given below.

2.1 Selected models

This sub-chapter gives a general overview of the models used and the purpose of each model. Below we will first discuss the fate models (in 2.1.1) and then the Exposure models, divided in human exposure models (2.1.2) and animal exposure models (2.1.3)

2.1.1 Fate models

To simulate the fate of pesticides in the environment the following models will be used:

- BROWSE: To calculate airborne concentrations as a result of drift, volatilization and dispersion of sprayed pesticides;
- PRZM: To calculate concentration in runoff;
- TOXSWA: To calculate concentrations in water and sediment from neighbouring water bodies.
- OBOdustpred: To calculate concentrations in indoor house dust.
- Wind erosion model (WindEro): To calculate airborne concentrations as a results of wind erosion.

Furthermore, existing data from previous studies in Portugal CSS, selected as one of the two-reference case studies for the modelling assessment, will be used to run PRZM and TOXSWA models. The outputs will be used as inputs for RIVWQ - CHEMICAL TRANSPORT MODEL FOR RIVERINE ENVIRONMENTS, for the assessment of pesticides concentrations in surface water and sediments at catchment level. However, the success and quality of the assessment will be highly influenced by the availability, the type and the abundance of the existing data. The actual SPRINT data collection and monitoring plans does not allow generating the data needed for a catchment scale assessment.

2.1.2 Human Exposure models

To simulate humans' exposure to pesticides, the following models will be used:

- OBOexposure: To calculate exposure via inhalation and dermal pathways, as well as dermal contact and incidental dust ingestion. The mathematical formulations are described in more detail in both [OBO \(2019\)](#) and SPRINT Milestone 3.

It is important to add that dietary exposure will be added to the above-mentioned model. This will be a probabilistic model based on the approaches discussed in [van der Voet et al. \(2014\)](#) for single-compound and cumulative dietary exposure.

The OBOexposure module will be transferred to R language, in order to be open-access and easily integrated in WP5 toolbox.

2.1.3 Animal exposure models

To simulate animals' exposure to pesticides, the following models will be used:

- Merlin-Expo: To calculate concentrations in fish (edible part) and cows (meat and milk).
- TERearthworm: For earthworms, we will calculate acute and chronic toxicity/exposure ratio (TER). Formulations are: $TER_{earthworm_{acute}} = LC50 / [C]_{soil}$ & $TER_{earthworm_{chronic}} = NOEC / [C]_{soil}$ (Where: $[C]_{soil}$ is the predicted concentration in soil; LC50: lethal concentration 50 %; NOEC: no observed effect concentration.)

2.2 Model chain

This sub-chapter presents the model chain and highlights the main inputs and outputs, as well as the evaluation steps

2.2.1 Model chain – Connections, Inputs & Outputs

The model connections and main inputs and outputs of each model are displayed in Figure 1. A more detailed list of all inputs can be found in annex I.

Figure 1. – Model chain, connections and most relevant inputs and outputs. *Note: Ground deposits refers to the fraction of spray drift that deposits, either via wet or dry deposition, on the O-Horizon soil layer. Concentration in the soil surface already includes other process such as washoff, photodegradation and evaporation from the soil layer. In more mass balance words: If t =time, and assuming that there are no pesticide residues in the soil: $C_{soil} = 0$ (at $t=0$), then there is application at $t=1$, which results in $C_{grounddeposit} = C_{soil}$, and at $t=2$ C_{soil} is no longer equal to ground deposit, because other process reduced concentration in soil*

In the model chain (Figure 1), we start by simulating pesticides fate in the environment. In short, each scenario starts with an application. The information regarding the application setting feeds into the BROWSE model. This information consists of reported sprayed volume, dose, active ingredient(s) present in the tank mixture and spraying technique. BROWSE consists of three components, which are i) emission into the air, water and ground deposited (PEARL model); ii) dispersion downwind (OPS-St model) and iii) exposure. For SPRINT only the first two components will be used, in order to estimate lateral drainage, gas-phase airborne concentrations (air), concentrations in soil surface and ground deposit (soil). The Wind erosion model (WindEro) will also estimate airborne concentrations but solely from particle-phase pesticides (bound to soil). The PRZM model will be run independently to calculate runoff and erosion fluxes. This, together with lateral drainage information, will serve as input to TOXSWA in order to estimate concentrations in the water and sediment. Finally, given that most people spent their time indoors,

concentrations in indoor dust will be calculated by using the OBODustpred model, which is an empirical model (created solely from observations).

The temporal scale will be hourly resolution. This only applies for simulations done at CSS level, it does not apply for simulations done in WP5.

All estimated concentrations will serve as input to the different exposure models. Each exposure model requires a set of different inputs, though concentration in the environmental matrix is the more important one. Many of the inputs are fixed (taken as average of the relevant population), but if information is available (e.g. literature) we will use distributions as input to the different exposure models. Detailed lists of required inputs can be found in each model respective documentation. For Merlin-expo, see <https://merlin-expo.eu/learn/documentation/>; For TERearthworm, see [Astaykina et al. 2020](#); For OBOexposure see [OBO 2019](#).

2.2.2 Evaluation of modelling results

In the two reference case studies, The Netherlands and Portugal, additional sampling will allow the collection of data needed for the verification of models simulations. In particular:

- **Toxswa** outputs will be compared with monitoring data of surface water and sediment, sampled during PPPs application (two sampling times), at the end of PPPs application (1 sampling) and after harvest (1 sampling maximum 2 weeks after).
- **Browse** outputs for **soil matrix** will be compared with the monitoring data collected at the end of PPPs application time and after harvest;
- **Browse** outputs for **ground deposit matrix** will be compared with the monitoring data collected each 15 days, for the entire year.;
- **Browse** and **WindEro** outputs for **air borne matrix** will be compared with the monitoring data collected each 15 days, for the entire year.

Furthermore, run-off and monitoring sediments and surface-water data from previous studies developed in Portugal may allow the verification and refinement of PRZM simulations as well as of RIVWQ - CHEMICAL TRANSPORT MODEL FOR RIVERINE ENVIRONMENTS, for pesticides concentrations in surface water and sediments at catchment level.

3. Wind erosion model (WindEro)

The Wind erosion model, from now on named WindEro, is being developed within the SPRINT project as a fate model. In this chapter we briefly present the scoping review on the existing mathematical formulations and approaches to calculate wind erosion of agricultural fields. We also give an update in the model development stage.

3.1 Scoping review on wind erosion calculation

For the development of the wind erosion model, a literature research in the SCOPUS database was made. This made it possible to assess the availability and the performance of existing models and to further develop the most suitable one for the purpose of the

SPRINT project. Research keywords and refinement rules as well as research outputs are here presented:

1. TITLE-ABS-KEY (wind AND erosion AND model); **2930 documents**
2. TITLE-ABS-KEY (wind AND erosion AND models) AND (LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2021) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2020) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2019) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2018) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2017)) AND (LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA , "ENVI") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA , "AGRI")); **385 documents**
3. TITLE-ABS-KEY (wind AND erosion AND model) AND (LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2021) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2020) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2019) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2018) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2017)) AND (LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA , "ENVI") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA , "AGRI")) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE , "English")); **350 documents**
4. TITLE-ABS-KEY (wind AND erosion AND models) AND (LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2021) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2020) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2019) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2018) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2017)) AND (LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA , "ENVI") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA , "AGRI")) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "ar")) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE , "English")); **302 documents**
5. (TITLE-ABS-KEY (wind AND erosion AND models) AND TITLE-ABS-KEY (pesticides) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (plant AND protection AND products)) AND (LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2021) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2019) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2018) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2017) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2014)) AND (LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA , "ENVI") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA , "AGRI")); **6 documents**
6. TITLE-ABS-KEY (wind AND erosion AND models) AND (LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2021) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2020) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2019) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2018) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2017)) AND (LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA , "ENVI") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA , "AGRI")) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "re")); **6 documents**
7. TITLE-ABS-KEY (wind AND erosion AND modelling) AND (LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2021) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2020) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2019) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2018) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2017)) AND (LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA , "ENVI") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA , "AGRI")); **186 articles**

From the 350 articles, found based on point 3 keywords and refinement rules, 302 articles were selected for the title check. After the title check, 85 articles were selected for a further abstract check and 26 articles were finally downloaded.

The review of the downloaded articles showed that some existing wind erosion models have varying degrees of complexity and specific capabilities as well as a range of spatial and temporal scales of application. Due to their uncertainties and limitations, their applicability to different regions and research questions is still under debate. However, based on models' applicability, expected validity, required databases, available outputs and source, the most suitable for SPRINT Project objectives were selected.

3.2 Model development

The wind erosion model development as already started. This is being written in R (programming language). The algorithm is based on the review by [Jarrah et al. 2020](#), and

case study applications reported by Pi et al. 2017 and Pi et al. 2020. In short, the eroded fraction is calculated based on weather conditions, such as wind speed and ambient air temperature, as well as other relevant conditions, such as surface roughness, vegetative cover factor, soil water content, soil erodibility factor, and others. Most of these variables are collected from each CSS.

4. Concluding remark

The fate and exposure models were selected and connections between the different models were established. These are based on the input-output relationship, without the need to merge models and allowing for i) changes and calibration in each module individually and ii) evaluate several outputs in the modelling steps, therefore reducing uncertainty propagation between modules.

The development of the WindEro script will soon be finished and after we will proceed to a third party code check. After this, the WindEro model will be suitable for use in the SPRINT modelling exercise.

However, as the results of the surveys and monitoring activities conducted in the CSS are not yet available and we do not know which matrices and what type of data will actually be available, we cannot provide a more detailed plan on which assessment will be carried out in each CSS.

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Annex I

Table A1.1 - Models and data overview

Model	Model application	Output	Used for?	Model verification data	Site specific data	Data frequency requirements
PRZM	Reference CSS and possible other CSS	runoff and erosion fluxes	TOXSWA runs	Existing data from CSS PT	<u>Longitude & Latitude</u> <u>Meteo data</u> -temperature	Not applicable
TOXSWA (field level)	Reference CSS and possible other CSS	concentrations in the surface <u>water layer</u> in horizontal direction only and in the <u>sediment layer</u> in both horizontal and vertical directions	aquatic organisms' exposure	-PPPs concentration in ditch water and sediment	(hourly/daily) -rainfall (hourly/daily) -wind speed (hourly/daily) - ET actual (daily) -solar radiation (daily) <u>Soil</u> -texture -organic matter content	5 sampling campaigns in a year
BROWSE (PEARL-OPS, new wind erosion module)	Reference CSS and possible other CSS	pesticide and metabolites <u>concentrations in soil</u>	soil organisms' exposure	- PPPs concentration in soil	<u>Soil</u> -texture -organic matter content -hydraulic properties	twice annually, end of PPP application time and after harvest
	Reference CSS	<u>concentrations in ground deposit</u>	input for human exposure	PPPs concentrations in ground deposit	-slope <u>Crop</u> -BBCH -leaf area	-sampler at 50 m from field - Each 15 days/1 month for 12 months
		<u>Concentration in air (airborne)</u>	input for human exposure	PPP concentration in air	-growing information <u>Water body</u> -Size -Depth -water flow velocity (m ³ /s) -distance from field <u>Agronomic management</u>	-sampler at 50 m from field - Weekly/ each 15 days/1 month for 12 months sampling at 0.5m and 2.0m above ground -sample flow rate 1L/min
OBO-Dustpred	Reference CSS	Concentrations in indoor house dust	input for human exposure	PPPs concentration in indoor house dust		1 additional indoor dust sample per household, collected before the start of the main sampling campaign for indoor dust. Minimum of 20 samples. Ideally 30 samples.